

Enhancing employee performance through training and development in the Zimbabwean construction sector: Insights from a volatile economic landscape

Liambo Freedom Tatenda¹; Chikukwa Tatenda²; Snehlanhla Mokoena³;

Lourens Elizabeth Melanie³; Mbona V. Sizwe⁵

PhD candidate, Faculty of Management Sciences¹; PhD, Faculty of Management Sciences²;

PhD, Faculty of Management Sciences³; PhD, Faculty of Management Sciences⁴,

PhD, Faculty of Applied Sciences⁵

Durban University of Technology, South Africa

Received: Aug 7 , 2025

Accepted: Sep 4, 2025

Published: Nov 4, 2025

Abstract

Employee performance plays a critical role in the effectiveness of a business and is integral in developing a competitive advantage in the fourth industrial revolution. Improving employee performance through training and development strategies will sustain organisational effectiveness and foster long-term success in the construction sector. This article seeks to investigate the effectiveness of training and development strategies in enhancing employee performance within the Zimbabwean construction sector. A quantitative research design was employed in investigating the relationship between the variables under study. In addition, a survey/census method was adopted in collecting data from 110 employees at KMP Holdings. A response rate of 82% was obtained and the collected data was analysed through various descriptive and inferential statistics. The results of the research study revealed that there is a statistically significant relationship between sample respondents' level of education and training and development and also that there is a statistically significant relationship between training and development and employee performance at KMP Holdings. The results show that organisations should ensure that employee performance is improved by providing the necessary training to achieve desired outcomes. Finally, the research study recommends that the organisation aligns employee training with prevailing technological advancements, continuously identify training needs, and also ensure that training and development opportunities are equally distributed.

Keywords: training and development, education, employee performance, skills, knowledge, human capital, construction sector

INTRODUCTION

According to Mella & Savage (2018), globally the construction sector represents approximately 13% of GDP and significantly plays a critical role in the advancement of countries especially developing countries. The construction sector in Zimbabwe is labour intensive, dynamic, complex, employs thousands of unskilled, semi-skilled and skilled workers and significantly contributes to economic growth and development in Zimbabwe. However, employers in developing countries are continuously reporting difficulties in finding skilled workers due to skills gaps and deficits as training programs are mostly out of date and do not meet industry expectations/needs. Construction workers in both the formal and informal sector are casually trained, have low educational attainments/qualifications. Riaz, Din & Aftab (2015) affirm that illiteracy and skills deficiency in the construction sector result in wastages, employee turnover, inequitable remuneration, insufficient employment opportunities, reduced and/or poor productivity, quality, health and safety.

Organisations acknowledge that well trained human resources/capital are critical for overall success and a sustainable competitive advantage as they cannot be easily imitated (Ozkeser, 2019). According to Ganesh & Indradevi (2015), training and developing the workforce leads to the maximum utilization of human resources through facilitating adaptation, increased/improved decision making and problem-solving capabilities among employees. This has the potential to increase and/or improve output, quality, employee morale, efficiency, organisational liability, flexibility and human relations (Ganesh & Indradevi, 2015). Apart from being a key indicator of organisations investing in employees, training and developing employees ensures that employees acquire new manipulative competencies i.e. Knowledge, Skills and Abilities (KSAs) that help in accomplishing objectives as well as contribute to organisational performance (Archieve, 2008). Despite various scholars highlighting the pivotal role of training and development, the construction sector in Zimbabwe is characterised by lack of construction projects, disregard for the rule of law and property rights and erratic government policies which have resulted in the total collapse of the economy (Moyo & Crafford, 2010). These challenges coupled with financial difficulties in Zimbabwe have severely affected the training and development efforts/initiatives in the construction sector.

The Pan African Research Service, as cited by Shora (2004) states that the construction industry in less economically developed countries is facing high structural constraints, such as skills shortages. Various types and qualities of skills are important in the construction sector, making investment in skills development of paramount consideration. However, the construction sector in Zimbabwe is faced with a shortage of critical skills and experienced employees such as project managers and qualified artisans resulting in failure to meet target time, cost and quality requirements (Shora, 2004; Blanchard, 2010). This is exacerbated by the continuous changes in technology that have resulted in skills redundancy as well as employers in the sector recruiting employees who do not possess adequate knowledge and experience to perform the job (Ngoc, 2009). While training and development is perceived to play a vital role in upskilling employees, there seems to be confusion/doubt as to the most effective skills acquisition strategies responsible for improved employee performance. Organisations in the construction sector can attain sustainable growth by generating technical skills and investments in training and development programmes/initiatives in line with construction sector needs. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the influence of training and development strategies on employee performance in the construction industry as organisational failure maybe a result of inadequate and/or poor training and development initiatives.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

Investing in training and development is vital as it can be useful in resolving organisational and/or management's problems as well as assist employees to actively participate in the realisation of organisational goals. Training and development initiatives are the foundation of improving and optimising employee productivity and/or performance through learning precise knowledge, skills and abilities. In addition, a positive culture towards developing employees and effectively implementing training and development initiatives is crucial in ensuring that both organisations and employees benefit. According to Noe (2018), training and development strategies relates to learning related actions that a company should adopt to achieve its strategy. Training is an organisational effort aimed at helping employees not only gain skills, abilities and knowledge but also helping employees change their attitudes, values and behaviour thereby facilitating effective functioning (Chikove & Shiri, 2023). Whilst training is concerned with specific job-related objectives, development entails a continuous

process to refine existing KSAs as well as exposing employees to be able to perform additional duties (Faridi & Baloch, 2019). Blanchard & James (2010) add that training and development initiatives are a part of an integrated system in which performance is evaluated based on an established criterion.

Literature identifies two dominant training strategies that an organisation can adopt namely, on the job training and off the job training (Tabassi, Ramli & Abu Bakar, 2011 and Bhattacharyya, 2019). According to Deb (2019), on the job training relies on existing employees to train and equip new recruits and the new recruit is placed on the job and the supervisor/mentor and/or manager shows the trainee how to do the job. Despite being an old technique, on the job training equips employees with skills to adapt to technological advancements as trainees are provided with facilities and resources as well as exposed to the prevailing environment (Estep 2008; Alrazehi & Amirah, 2020). Nel, Werner, Haasbroek, Poisat, Sono & Schults (2018) and Erasmus, Loedolff, du Plessis, Mda & Nel (2019) assert that on-the-job training strategies include organisations using job rotation, committee assignments, understudy assignments, apprenticeship, coaching, secondments, lateral transfers, mentoring and action learning. On the job training has various advantages which include saving costs as it doesn't require special training facilities; it is also specific to the individual and business; the trainee gets advice immediately; and that the trainee is productive during training (Medina, 2006; De Silva, 2020).

However, it is also key to note that on the job training may also have drawbacks which include the possibility of the trainer not being good at training; work not being of good quality; potential for costly errors by the trainee; training may take lower priority; training restricts opportunities for the trainee; and it is not easy to train a group of trainees (Medina 2006; De Silva, 2020). Deb (2019) states that off the job training relates to learning by gaining knowledge through various techniques such as discussions, individualised tutorials, demonstrations, lectures, simulations, role plays, sensitivity training and other forms of training done outside the work environment. The development may be conducted by an internal training department or outsourced to training specialists. Off the job training is less risky; inspires trainees to work on their growth and development; allows trainees to concentrate without distractions (Palmer, 2007; Panagiotakopoulos, 2019). However, off the job training also possesses disadvantages such as being expensive; difficulty in applying skills in real situations (Palmer, 2007; Panagiotakopoulos, 2019). An organisation's training strategy is primarily influenced by the business environment, organizational goals, available

resources, and an understanding of the necessity for competitive advantage within the construction sector. Bhattacharyya (2019) affirms that training strategies are aimed at developing an employee's core competencies (KSAs) and attitudes as they are paramount in enhancing creative thinking, problem solving, self-development, organisational competitiveness and the overall success or failure of the organisation.

Employee performance improvement is a big concern for organisational leaders and one of the most critical elements a training strategy should possess (Quick & Nelson, 2013 and Govender & Busin 2020). Continuous training is required to review and update the knowledge and skills of employees as it makes them functionally effective in their performance. According to Elaine & Leslie (2019), employee performance refers to employee output in terms of quantity and quality expected from each employee in a particular job. In addition, Pekuri, Haapasalo & Herrala (2011) state that performance involves aspects such as excellence and productivity among other non-cost factors such as quality, speed, delivery and flexibility. When performance is high, employees work in the shortest possible time with the least expenditure or inputs without sacrificing quality with minimum wastage of resources. Blanchard & James (2010) affirm that obtaining improved employee performance levels from improved capability are a performance management challenge. Quick & Nelson (2013) and Crawshaw, Budhwar & Davis (2023) emphasise that performance goals must be clearly defined and understood by employees who are expected to perform effectively and efficiently at work. Wright & Geroy (2010) also emphasise that for employees to perform higher, training and development strategies should develop effective employees' skills to the point where they show initiative. Herholdt (2012) states that one of the employee performance drivers is to develop the competencies to identify and grow talent in the organisation. Management must define what is expected from the employees, and that they stay focused on effective employee performance (Villanova as cited by Stahl & Bjorkman, 2006). Managers must also be able to assess the extent to which employees have achieved the goals that were set.

In respect of the different professional disciplines of African qualified employees, training and development of employees creates flexible and highly skilled employees and an integral part of improved employee performance. Quality training and development is directly linked to improved employee performance. This is because quality training initiatives are an enabling strategy in empowering and enabling employees to be confident in using and adapting to new technologies, progressively adjust to environmental changes and also

improve their deficiencies and/or shortcomings in a structured manner (Deb, 2009; Dyke, Nel & Loedolf, 2010; and Khan, 2017). In addition, Faridi & Baloch (2019) acknowledge that training and development initiatives help with the optimal utilisation of resources and has both short-term and long-term benefits for both individuals (improved performance, knowledge accumulation, employee empowerment, commitment, etc) and organisations (improved performance, better productivity, increased employee performance, lower turnover/retention, realisation of objectives, market growth). Asfaw, Argaw, & Bayissa (2015) and Armstrong (2013:215) highlight the significance of training and development within organisations to enhance employee capabilities and improve proficiency, efficiency, and effectiveness. These initiatives are designed to boost performance and productivity while fostering individual growth to address the organisation's human resource requirements. Furthermore, Tahir, Yousafzai, Jan & Hashim (2014) stress the importance of implementing these strategies, which not only advance organisational goals but also benefit the employees. Effective training and development programs contribute to increased profitability, foster positive attitudes toward employee performance, and enhance job knowledge, all while aligning with the organisation's objectives and refining task performance. Thus, training and development are essential in improving employee performance (Chaudhry, Jariko, Mushtaque, Mahesar & Ghani, 2017).

Lack of top management support, no clear link between training and organisational goals and plans; inadequate/incorrect accounting of training costs; limited/inadequate training needs analysis/assessment; lack of support for applying new skills and knowledge on the job; lack of meaningful evaluation of training initiatives are key indicators of ineffective training (Rehman, Khan & Khan, 2011). Despite difficulties associated with setting measurable objectives and evaluating training initiatives and/or processes, reviews by training officers, line manager and/or trainees during and after training completion are key (training officer, line manager, trainees) in ensuring that training is effective (Manzini & Shumba, 2014). From the above, it is evident that the effect of training and development initiatives on addressing inefficiencies, improving organisational effectiveness and competitiveness cannot be underestimated. However, despite the above individual and organisational benefits, evidence from previous studies have highlighted that the need for effective training and accountability for training initiatives has increased due to the questionable effect of training initiatives. Therefore, this research study seeks to investigate the intricate relationship between training and development and employee performance in a volatile economic environment. Moreover,

to examine the relationship between training and development and employee performance, the research study will test the following hypothesis:

- H₁: There is a significant relationship between level of education and training and development opportunities,
- H₂: There is a significant relationship between level of education and employee performance,
- H₃: There is a significant relationship between training and development and employee performance.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The methods section provides an overview of the research methodology and design, focusing on the organised collection and analysis of data to address specific research questions. The research study adopted a quantitative descriptive research design aimed at ensuring credible and precise data collection processes. A quantitative research design is dependent on collecting numerical data and examining correlations/co-variations between independent and dependent variables (Panke, 2018). A survey/census method was adopted in eliciting responses from 110 employees at KMP Holdings as the sample was too small to warrant sampling. The measuring instrument, a structured questionnaire with close-ended questions, was carefully developed and validated through a pilot study to ensure its reliability and validity (results in Table 2). The structured questionnaire was distributed to all the employees at KMP Holdings and 90 (82% response rate) completed questionnaires were captured to form a data set. The collected and captured data was analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics thereby facilitating a thorough evaluation of the research findings which are essential for hypothesis testing and deriving meaningful conclusions regarding the effects of training and development on employee performance. Moreover, ethical considerations, including informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality, were prioritised to safeguard participant information and encourage candid responses.

This study comprises of descriptive statistics which utilized frequency tables and display charts to deliver information on key demographic variables in the study. The target population for this study was 110 employees from KMP Holdings in Mutare, Zimbabwe. A total of 110 respondents received structured questionnaires which were distributed by the researcher using the personal method. Twenty questionnaires were removed since the majority of statements were left unanswered. Hence this equated to 90 responses therefore

82% response rate was obtained. Table 1 summarizes the demographic information of the respondents. Male respondents were 63 (70%) and 27 (30%) were females. Researchers observed that majority of the respondents (41.1%) were aged 25 to 29 years, followed by those in the age group 30 to 34 years (21.1%), 20 to 24 years (15.6%), 35 to 39 years (14.4%), and those who were 40 years and above, representing only 7.8% of the respondents. The analysis revealed that the majority of the respondents (62.2%) were between 25-34 years of age. Most (36.7%) of the respondents had 6-9 years working experience with KPM Holdings. A total of 33.3% of the respondents had 1-5 years of service. Meanwhile, 15.6% had less than 1 year of service; and 12.2% of respondents fell between 10-14 years of service. A meagre 2.2% of the respondents had 15 years and above of service at KMP Holdings. Furthermore, a total of 37.8% respondents had a certificate as their highest qualification while 21.1% were in possession of a Diploma, 4.4% had a post-graduate qualification, whilst 22.2% had other qualifications.

Table 1: Demographic information of the respondents

Variables	Categories	n (%)
Gender	Male	63 (70.0)
	Female	27 (30.0)
Age group in years	20 to 24	14 (15.6)
	25 to 29	37 (41.1)
	30 to 34	19 (21.1)
	35 to 39	13 (14.4)
	40 and above	7 (7.8)
How long have you been with this Company?	Less than 1 year	14 (15.6)
	1 - 5 years	30 (33.3)
	6 - 9 years	33 (36.7)
	10 - 14 years	11 (12.2)
	More than 14 years	2 (2.2)
Highest Qualification attained	Certificate	34 (37.8)
	Diploma	19 (21.1)
	Degree	13 (14.4)
	Post graduate degree	4 (4.4)
	Others	20 (22.2)

Table 2 below presents Likert scale responses in terms of mean and standard deviation for sections B and C. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for both sections was also presented. In these sections, each item was measured using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 stand for strongly agree and 5 stands for strongly disagree. In order to make interpretation simple, researchers used the following coding system. The mean value between (1 – 2.99) indicates agreement, (3) indicates neutral, and (3.01 – 5) indicates disagreement. Based on the results, there is an indication that respondents disagreed to the items (B1, B2, B5, B7, C2, C3, C8 and C10). For instance, the estimated mean value to the statement 'The training meets my needs for my current job' is 4.01. This is an indication that respondents were not happy with the training they get in their current job. Again, majority of the respondents disagreed to the statement 'I get feedback on my performance standards', the estimated mean value was 3.96. The internal consistency of the items in both sections was confirmed by calculating Cronbach's alpha to test reliability of the items. Reliability denotes the consistency with which a research tool measure what it is supposed to measure (Ragin & Amoroso, 2011). Researchers of this study carefully phrased each of the items (statements) to avoid ambiguity which would lead respondents to particular answers. The value for Cronbach's alpha was greater than threshold of 0.6 (Bagozzi and Yi's, 1998; Bryman, 2015), which showed a degree of consistency and reliable of the items. The overall Cronbach's alpha was greater than 0.7.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

Table 2: The mean, standard deviation and Cronbach's alpha coefficient for items measuring 'training and development' and 'employee performance'

Section	Item	Item statement	Mean (SD)	Cronbach's alpha
Training and development	B1	The company provides the training that I need to do my job well.	3.97 (0.977)	0.621
	B2	The training meets my needs for my current job.	4.01 (0.855)	
	B3	All training and development initiatives had been made aware to me.	2.50 (1.368)	
	B4	The organisation provided me with necessary resources to use my newly acquired skills.	2.32 (1.150)	
	B5	Training and development strategies are conducted successfully on the job.	3.73 (1.207)	
	B6	The training and development strategies that are provided in my workplace equip me with knowledge and skills to be able to perform effectively.	2.36 (1.368)	
	B7	I am able to transfer the knowledge and skills that I acquired through training and development strategies back to my job situation.	3.73 (1.207)	
Employee Performance	C1	My performance is determined by the methods that I use to perform a task.	2.21 (1.096)	0.739
	C2	There is a clear link between my skill shortcoming and training provided.	3.81 (0.959)	
	C3	The work environment supports me to perform the best out of my abilities.	3.76 (1.084)	
	C4	My performance is improving due to	2.66	

	training and development provided.	(1.325)
C5	I feel comfortable when performing my duties.	2.28 (1.092)
C6	Clear methods of performing tasks lead to my efficiency and effectiveness.	2.66 (1.219)
C7	Different methods of carrying out a task affect the performance.	2.84 (1.189)
C8	I get feedback on my performance standards.	3.96 (0.993)
C9	The company undertakes performance appraisal exercise.	2.19 (1.048)
C10	The working conditions permit me to perform well.	3.77 (1.181)
Overall		0.711

In table 3, Anova tested whether there is any statistically significant difference between qualifications of the respondents in terms of training and development. Results in Table 4 indicate that there was no relationship between training and development and the qualification of the respondents (F-value = 0.752; p-value = 0.559). Thus, hypothesis one (H_1) is rejected.

Table 3: ANOVA testing difference between qualifications in terms of training and development

Training and development					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.731	4	0.183	0.752	0.559
Within Groups	20.640	85	0.243		
Total	21.371	89			

**Statistically significant at p-value < 0.05*

Table 4: ANOVA testing difference between qualifications in terms of employee performance

Employee performance					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.810	4	0.203	2.088	0.024*
Within Groups	8.246	85	0.097		
Total	9.057	89			

*Statistically significant at p -value < 0.05

In Table 4, Anova tested whether there is any statistically significant difference between qualifications of the respondents in terms of employee performance. Results in Table 4 indicate that employee performance based was significantly similar with regards to the qualification of the respondents (F-value = 2.088; p -value = 0.024). Since $p < 0.05$, there is a statistically significant relationship between the sample respondents' level of education and employee performance. Therefore, hypothesis two (H_2) is accepted.

Table 5: Correlation between training and development, and employee performance

	Spearman's rho	p-value	95% Confidence Intervals	
			Lower	Upper
Training and development ↔ Employee performance	0.755	0.038*	0.460	0.965

*Statistically significant at p -value < 0.05

Table 5 depicts the relationship between training and development and employee performance at a selected construction company in Zimbabwe. The Spearman's rho shows that $r = 0.755$ and $p = 0.038$. Therefore, there is a statistically significant relationship

between training and development ($p < 0.05$) at the selected construction company in Zimbabwe. Thus, hypothesis three (H_3) is accepted.

DISCUSSION

Firstly, the research study revealed that educational levels have a positive and statistically significant relationship with employee performance. Kasika (2015) found that educational attainment had a statistically significant effect on job performance amongst employees at the Social Security Commission in Namibia. This is in line with findings by Ning, Wang & Zheng (2018); Asif & Naeem (2019); Stoffberg, Ferreira & Twum-Darko (2023); Milang, Firmansyah & Sibay (2024) and Rebecca (2024) who found that educational attainment/qualifications positively and significantly impact individual and/or employee performance. In addition, Aliata & Ligare (2021) also found that the level of education is a mediator in the relationship between human resource practices and employee performance whilst Akpezi & Amah (2024) concluded that educational level has a significant effect on job outcomes and improved organisational performance. From the aforementioned findings, it is evident that education is essential in enhancing human, social and economic development. The above results seem to suggest that organisations use education as a yardstick/indicator of an employee's productivity and that the higher the educational attainment, the greater the positive effect of education and skill on job and/or employee performance (Akpezi & Amah, 2024). Educated employees demonstrate improved performance as they are more receptive to receiving instructions, executing tasks and adapting to new technologies (Kasika, 2015).

Secondly, the research study concluded that training and development is positively related to employee performance. These results support the results from a study in the South African construction sector by Kum, Cowden & Karodia (2014) that concluded that training and development helps employees adapt to new developments as well as improving employee behaviour and employee performance. Research studies by Bangura (2017); Landa (2018); Karim, Choudhury & Latif (2019); Luo, Ma & Li (2021); Mehale, Govender & Mabaso (2021); Nama, Daweti, Lourens & Chikukwa (2022); Nwali & Adegunle (2021); Yimam (2022); and Gebrehiwot & Elantheraiyan (2023) revealed that training and development positively affect employee performance and that investing in training and development results in tangible benefits (return on investment). In their study, Iruobe, Ojambati, Akinpade & Iruobe (2012) found that sufficient/adequate employee training is of paramount importance

to the successful implementation of TQM in the construction sector. In addition, a trend analysis between 1999 and 2010 by Dixit, Mandal, Sawhney & Singh (2017) revealed that skills development positively influences productivity in the construction sector. The process of improving employee performance through skills development is a collaborative effort between the organisation and employees that is mutually beneficial. For instance, according to Erasmus & Loedolff (2019) and Arulsamy, Singh, Kumar, Panchal & Bajaj (2023), organisations can gain significant advantages from training and development initiatives such as enhanced productivity, improved customer satisfaction, and the development of talent whilst employees benefit through improved employee loyalty, job satisfaction, engagement and empowerment to make decisions and solve problems. Moreover, the human capital theory suggests that investments in human capital through education, training and development have significantly increased employee productivity and/or performance through increasing essential competencies and operational capabilities (Lanre-Babalola, Oginni, Ajobola, Oluwu, Balogun, Tewogbade, Iori & Gbotosho, 2023).

The aforementioned evidence on the relationship between training initiatives and employee performance indicates that a strategic approach to skills development not only equips employees with skills and knowledge but also fosters a culture of lifelong learning and adaptability (Saxena, 2024). Odhiambo (2018) affirms that employee training and development initiatives assist in bridging the gap by bringing employees up to but not beyond the desired expected standard/competence. However, Sekgala & Holtzhausen (2016) suggest that in order to accurately evaluate the role of training and development on employee performance enhancement, it is essential to assess and measure the effectiveness of skills development programs. Arulsamy *et al* (2023) add that it is vital for organisations to establish a robust framework that encourages learning, adaptability and progress thereby allowing organisations to leverage employees' skills effectively in tackling current challenges and drive future initiatives.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of the research study was to examine the effect of training and development on employee performance in a volatile economic environment. Construction companies that emphasise human resource management recognize that skills development is vital for enhancing employee performance and productivity. Employees are fundamentally the best

assets to an organisation in the construction sector and most importantly, they ought to be treated as human capital. The more organisations invest in human capital, the more can be anticipated from them regarding performance behaviour, which can automatically give the organisation a sustainable competitive advantage. Investing in these programs not only yields a positive return on investment but also acknowledges employees as valuable assets. A well-organised training strategy enhances quality and minimises errors, while effective appraisal processes and feedback mechanisms help identify areas for improvement. Moreover, ongoing development initiatives foster a skilled workforce capable of adapting to employee turnover. Additionally, individual self-assessment plays a critical role in enabling employees to identify their personal growth opportunities. Financing skills development programs is important for any organisation, which will certainly recognize and gain a return on its investment in training and developing strategies for its workers. The study presents several recommendations for enhancing employee performance at KMP Holdings in Zimbabwe. Firstly, it is essential to improve working conditions, as adverse environments can diminish employee commitment. Providing constructive feedback following training sessions assists employees in recognising areas for growth, while ensuring sufficient resources for training facilitates the acquisition of necessary skills. Increasing the frequency of training programs empowers employees with new knowledge, and aligning training initiatives with the latest technological advancements maintains the relevance of their skills. Effective training can also decrease the reliance on managerial oversight, and offering job-specific training promotes internal career development. Lastly, clearly communicating training objectives boosts motivation and fosters collaboration among employees. It is imperative for management to engage in open dialogue and utilise multiple communication platforms to disseminate information effectively.

REFERENCES

1. Akpezi, O.G. & Amah, E. 2024. The Relationship between Education Levels and Job Outcomes. *International Academic Journal of Management and Marketing*, 11(1): 59 – 69.
2. Aliata, V.L. & Ligare, B.S. 2021. Influence of education level on the relationship between human resource practices and employee performance among the administration police in Influence of education level on the relationship between

- human resource practices and employee performance among. *International Journal of Research in Human Resource Management*, 3(1), p.7.
3. Alrazehi, H. & Amirah, N.A. 2020. A review of training and development towards employee retention in the banking sector. *The Journal of Management Theory and Practice (JMTP)*, pp.16-21.
 4. Alrazehi, H. & Amirah, N.A. 2020. A review of training and development towards employee retention in the banking sector. *The Journal of Management Theory and Practice (JMTP)*, pp.16-21.
 5. Archieve, B. 2008. *Effect of Training and Manpower Development on Productivity of Workers*. New York: Harper and Row Publishers.
 6. Armstrong, M. 2013. *Blending formal and informal approaches to management learning*. New York: Mc Graw Hill Book Co.
 7. Arulsamy, A.S., Singh, I., Kumar, M.S., Panchal, J.J. & Bajaj, K.K. 2023. Employee training and development enhancing employee performance—A study. *Samdarshi*, 16(3), pp.406-416.
 8. Asfaw, A.M., Argaw, M.D. & Bayissa, L. 2015. The Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance and Effectiveness: A Case Study of District Five Administration Office, Bole Sub-City, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. 3: 188-202.
 9. Asif, R. & Naeem, A. 2019. Relationship between Level of Educational Attainment and Employee Performance: Mediating Role of Individual Religious Affiliation. *Bannu University Research Journal in Islamic Studies*, 6(1).
 10. Bagozzi, R.P., & Yi, Y. 1988. On the evaluation of structural equation models. *Journal of Academy of Marketing Science*, 16(1), 74 - 95.
 11. Bangura, S. 2017. Effect of training and development on employee performance at an academic advising centre in Durban. *Educor Multidisciplinary Journal*, 1(1), pp.30-46.
 12. Bhattacharrya, D. 2009. *Human resources management*. 2nd Edition. New Delhi: Pearson education Inc.
 13. Björkman, I. & Stahl, G.K. 2006. 1 International human resource management research: an introduction to the field. *Handbook of research in international human resource management*, p.1.
 14. Blanchard, P. & James, W. 2010. *Effective training systems, strategies and practices*. New Jersey: Pearson education Inc.

15. Bryman, A. & Bell, E. 2015. *Business research methods*. New York: Oxford University Press.
16. Chaudhry, N.I., Jariko, M.A., Mushtaque, T., Mahesar, H.A. & Ghani, Z., 2017. Impact of working environment and training & development on organisation performance through mediating role of employee engagement and job satisfaction. *European Journal of Training and Development Studies*, 4(2), pp.33-48.
17. Chikove, M. & Shiri, A., 2021. The Effect of leadership style on employee commitment in the mining sector in Zimbabwe.
18. Crawshaw, J., Budhwar, P. & Davis, A. 2023. *Human resource management, strategic and international perspectives*. 4th ed. SAGE Publications: Chennai.
19. De Silva, T., 2020. *Integrating business management processes: Volume 2: Support and assurance processes*. Productivity Press.
20. Deb, T. 2009. *Performance Appraisal and Management: concept, antecedents and implications*. New Delhi: Excel Book.
21. Dixit, S., Mandal, S.N., Sawhney, A. & Singh, S. 2017. Relationship between skill development and productivity in the construction sector: A literature review. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 8(8), pp.649-665.
22. Elaine, W. & Leslie D.C. 2009. Service Employee Performance: *Journal of Relationship Marketing*. 8(2): 82-102.
23. Erasmus, B. & Loedolff, P. 2019. *Managing training and development*. 8th edition. Cape Town: Oxford University Press Southern Africa (Pty) Ltd.
24. Estep, T. 2008. *The Evolution of the Training Profession*. ASTD Handbook for Workplace Learning Professionals. New York: ASTD Press.
25. Faridi, A. & Baloch, A., 2019. Training and development methods affecting professionalism and empowerment of banking sector employees. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 6(2), pp.75-92.
26. Ganesh, M. & Indradevi, R., 2015. Importance and effectiveness of training and development. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(1).
27. Gebrehiwot, G.D. & Elantheraiyan, P., 2023. A study on the effect of training on employee performance in the case of Mekelle City, Tigray, Ethiopia. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 8(1), p.100567.
28. Govender, M. & Bussin, M.H. 2020. Performance management and employee engagement: A South African perspective. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 18(1), pp.1-19.

29. Herholdt, J. (Ed.). 2012. *Managing Change in Organisations: Articles from Human Capital Review*. Knowres Publishing.
30. Iruobe, O.J., Ojambati, T.S., Akinpade, J.A. & Iruobe, T. 2012. An investigation into the impact of total quality management application in the construction industry (a case of training). *Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 3(2), pp.344-348.
31. Karim, M.M., Choudhury, M.M. & Latif, W.B., 2019. The impact of training and development on employees' performance: an analysis of quantitative data. *Noble International Journal of Business and Management Research*, 3(2), pp.25-33.
32. Kasika, B.D., 2015. *The effect of educational qualification on job performance: the case of Social Security Commission in Namibia (SSC)* (Doctoral dissertation).
33. Khan, N. 2017. Adaptive or Transactional Leadership in Current Higher Education: A Brief Comparison. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 18, 178-183.
34. Khan, R.A., 2011. Measuring training effectiveness: A case study of public sector project management in Pakistan. *Journal of Diversity Management—First Quarter*, 6(1), pp.39-48.
35. Kum, F.D., Cowden, R. & Karodia, A.M. 2014. The impact of training and development on employee performance: A case study of ESCON Consulting. *Singapore journal of business economics and management studies*, 3(3): 72 – 105.
36. Landa, E. 2018. Influence of training on employees performance in public institution in tanzania. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 8(2), p.324.
37. Lanre-Babalola, F.O., Oginni, B.O., Ajibola, K.S., Olowu, A.E., Balogun, R.A., Tewogbade, S.O., Ilori, O.A. & Gbotosho, A.S., 2023. Human capital development and employee performance: Evidence from Osun State Ministry of Human Resource and Capacity Building, Nigeria. *Journal of Behavioural Studies*, 4(2).
38. Luo, Z., Ma, E. & Li, A., 2021. Driving frontline employees performance through mentorship, training, and interpersonal helping: The case of upscale hotels in China. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 23(5), pp.846-857.
39. Manzini, S. & Shumba, V. 2014. An investigation into the Impact of Training and Development on the Performance of Public Servants at the Passport Office in Bulawayo, Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 1(1).

40. Medina, R. 2006. *Personnel & Human Resources Management'2006 Ed.* Rex Bookstore, Inc..
41. Mehale, K.D., Govender, C.M. & Mabaso, C.M., 2021. Maximising training evaluation for employee performance improvement. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management, 19*, p.11.
42. Mella, A. & Savage, M., 2018. Construction sector employment in low income countries. *ICED and DFID.* https://www.academia.edu/36965702/Construction_Sector_Employment_in_Low_Income_Countries_Construction_Sector_Employment_in_Low_Income_Countries.
43. Milang, I., Firmansyah, A. & Sibay, Y.F., 2024. The Role of Education Level on Employee Performance. *Journal of Management, 3(1)*, pp.66-69.
44. Moyo, A. & Crafford, G., 2010. The impact of hyperinflation on the Zimbabwean construction sector. *Acta Structilia: Journal for the Physical and Development Sciences, 17(2)*, pp.53-83.
45. Nel, P.S., Werner A., Haasbroek, G.D., Poisat, P., Sono, T. & Schultz, H.B. 2008. *Human Resources Management. 7th edition.* Cape Town: Oxford University Press
46. Nelson, D. L. & Quick, J. C. 2013. *Organisational Behaviour: Science, the Real World, and You.* Cengage Learning.
47. Ngoc, T.N. 2009. *Intelligent Systems for Knowledge Management.* Berlin: Springer-Verlag
48. Ning, N., Wang, J., Lin, Z. & Zheng, Z., 2018. The direct and moderating effect of learning orientation on individual performance in the banking industry in China: contextualization of high-performance work systems. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources, 56(3)*, pp.360-383.
49. Noe, R.A. 2007. *Employee training and development.* 3rd Edition. New York: The McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
50. Nwali, N. & Adekunle, M., 2021. Does training and development impact the employee performance or another ritual? *Applied Journal of Economics, Management and Social Sciences, 2(1)*, pp.42-48.
51. Odhiambo, J.O. 2018. *Effect of training and development on employee performance at Safaricom Company Limited* (Doctoral dissertation, Kca University).
52. Ozkeser, B. 2019. Impact of training on employee motivation in human resources management. *Procedia Computer Science, 158*, pp.802-810.

53. Panke, D. 2018. Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-method projects: how to make the choice. In *Research Design & Method Selection: Making Good Choices in the Social Sciences* (Vol. 0, pp.). SAGE Publications Ltd., <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781529682700>.
54. Pekuri, A., Haapasalo, H. & Herrala M. 2011. Productivity and performance management – managerial practices in the construction sector. *International Journal of Performance Measurement*, 1 (1), 39-58
55. Ragin, C. C., & Amoroso, L. M. 2011. *Constructing social research: The unity and diversity of method*. Pine Forge Press.
56. Rebecca, W., 2024. An assessment of the impact of educational qualifications on employee job performance among Ghanaian university administrative staff. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 6(3), pp.988-1002.
57. Riaz, Z., Din, Z.U. & Aftab, U., 2015. Training of construction workers in Pakistan.
58. Saxena, D.P. 2024. The Role of Employee Training and Development in Enhancing Workplace Productivity. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377895933_The_Role_of_Employee_Training_and_Development_in_Enhancing_Workplace_Productivity#full-text. Date accessed: 26 October 2024.
59. Shora, R. M. 2004. *Training and Development*. Harare: Z.O.U.
60. Stoffberg, J. Ferreira, L.N. & Twum-Darko, M. 2023. *The relevance of educational qualifications to job performance among academic administrators at a University*. *International Journal of Higher Education*; 12(1): 70-82.
61. Tabassi, A., Ramli, M. & Baha, A. 2011. training and development of workforces in construction sector. *International journal of academic research*, 3(4): 509-515.
62. Tahir, N., Yousafzai, I.K., Jan, S. & Hashim, M., 2014. The impact of training and development on employees performance and productivity a case study of United Bank Limited Peshawar City, KPK, Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(4), p.86.
63. Van Dyke, P., Nel, P., Leodolff, Z., Van, P. & Haasbroek, T. 2010. *Training management*. 3rd Edition. New York: Oxford University Press.
64. Wright, P. & Geroy, D.G. 2011, “Changing the mindset: the training myth and the need for world-class performance”. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 12(4): 586-600. 124